

Hysteresis in Water Vapour Sorption and Desorption on Guar Gum

S. L. Gupta and R. K. S. Bhatia

Investigations of the series of sorptions and desorptions of water vapour on natural organic colloids like gelatin¹, gum arabic² and ghatti gum³ have revealed the phenomenon of the disappearance of the hysteresis effect initially exhibited. Guar gum (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) has shown certain unique and interesting characteristics in the sorption and desorption of water vapour and these are reported in this note.

Complete sorption and desorption isotherms, at 35°, of water vapour on guar gum were obtained gravimetrically, using a McBain-Bakr balance⁴. The study was continued up to 9th cycle. The loops obtained at the 1st, 3rd, 5th and 9th cycles are shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Sorption-desorption hysteresis of water vapour on Guar gum at the 1st, 3rd, 5th and 9th cycles.

The hysteresis loop changes in shape and size on successive sorptions and desorptions. In the low and high vapour pressure regions of the first cycle there are loops. In the middle the sorption-desorption curves are coincident. It is a case of "split hysteresis loop". After the 3rd cycle, hysteresis effect in the high vapour pressure region is completely removed. On successive sorptions and desorptions the desorption curve shifts away from

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the sorption curve. This shift is quite predominant in the low vapour pressure region of the hysteresis loop in the 9th cycle. There is also a decrease in the total sorptive capacity from 66.1% of the 1st cycle to 62.3% of the 9th cycle. Part of the sorption curve in the high vapour pressure region has slightly shifted towards the pressure axis.

Sorption-desorption hysteresis can be looked upon as a blockage effect of the smaller capillaries which may stay filled during desorption and prevent the connecting-larger ones from being properly emptied. The difference between the radii of the smaller and the connecting bigger capillaries is a measure of the volume of the liquid entrapped.

Guar gum in contact with water vapour is essentially a changing system. During successive sorptions and desorptions it is subjected to successive swelling and shrinkage. The slight decrease in the total sorptive capacity and increase in the entrapping effect in the low vapour pressure region suggest that the smaller capillaries are more constricted than the connecting bigger capillaries. In a swelling system, in a solvating liquid, the entry of the liquid into the interior is a slow process. The hydration and swelling may not be uniform. During desorption, the swollen adsorbent shrinks. Swelling and shrinkage, if non-uniform, result in localised stresses and strains and probably these affect the extent of collapse of the smaller capillaries and bigger bodies. The nature of changes observed in guar gum in the 9th cycle is a particular stage in the continuous process. If further sorptions and desorptions were continued on the same adsorbent the smaller necks would further shrink and finally collapse and the hysteresis loop would have disappeared.

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Department of Chemistry,
Birla Institute of Technology and Science,
Pilani, Raj.

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